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A Study on the Battle of Aberdeen

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Introduction :

The Andaman and Nicobar Islands is a union territory of India consisting of 572 islands, of which 37 are inhabited, at the junction of the Bay of Bengal and the Andaman Sea. The Andaman Sea lies to the east and the Bay of Bengal to the west. The Andaman Islands are also home to the Sentinelese people, an uncontacted tribe. The Sentinelese might be the only people currently known to not have reached further than a Paleolithic level of technology; however, this is disputed, as evidence of metalwork was found on their island. The earliest archaeological evidence documents some 2,200 years. However, genetic and cultural studies suggest that the indigenous Andamanese people may have been isolated from other populations during the Middle Paleolithic, which ended 30,000 years ago. Since that time, the Andamanese have diversified into linguistically and culturally distinct territorial groups.

The Nicobar Islands appear to have been populated by people of various backgrounds. By the time of European contact, the indigenous inhabitants had coalesced into the Nicobarese people, speaking an Austroasiatic language, and the Shompen, whose language is of uncertain affiliation. Neither language is related to Andamanese.

Battle of Aberdeen :

The Battle of Aberdeen on the Andaman Islands, fought in 1859, was a wonderfully hushed affair in Victorian consciousness. The battle was fought by the Andamanese tribe Jarawa, with bow-and-arrows, against heavy British musketry. The leading role played by Doodnath Tiwari, who is the son of a Brahmin family member Thakoor Tiwari, was a Sepoy of the 14th Infantry of Bengal Army. He was, on the wake of 1857 Mutiny, convicted of mutiny and desertion on 27 September 1857, by the Commission of Jhelum and was sentenced to transportation beyond the seas for life. Tiwari, convict number 276, had escaped on 6 April 1858 with several other prisoners from Ross Island and had been taken prisoner by the tribals after the others had been killed. Tiwari had then been luckily accepted and allowed to live with the tribals; hence he resided with the natives and even made to marry two tribal girls. After a long stay for one year and twenty - four days in the Andaman jungles, he voluntarily returned to the convict station at Aberdeen, Port Blair, on 17 May 1859, to report of an attack plotted by the aborigines against the convict station, which was later named as the 'Battle of Aberdeen'.

The Tribes undertook three major raids on 6th April, on 14th April and on 17th of May, 1859. In the last raid there was large scale participation of the indigenes who attempted a well organised raid on the Aberdeen Station with the aim to exterminate the British. Their last raid is known as the Battle of Aberdeen. But Doodnath betrayed the tribe by passing on information to the Superintendent of the Penal settlement. The results of the battle were terrifying as a large number of Andamanese tribes were killed in a single day.

After the battle, his statement was recorded at Ross Island in the Superintendent's Court, by Dr. J.P. Walker from 26 May to 4 June 1859. The statement that the court records, at a later stage, becomes valuable for the British as well as ethnographers to identify the customs, habits and traditions pertaining to such tribes in the Andamans.

Conclusion :

In order to commemorate the Battle of Aberdeen a monument was built in memory of those Andamanese aborigines who bravely fought the Battle of Aberdeen

in May 1859, at port Blair. Although it is clearly shows that if Tiwari has managed at that time then there is no place of Battle of Aberdeen by conveying the natives regarding the powers of advancement by saying as Bullets are more powerful than Arrows. Still on every 17th of May, islanders pay their tributes to those Andamanese warriors who with their primitive weapons fought the largest empire of all time.

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